

Eliminate shape restrictions with **MOLDED PLASTIC MAGNETS**

A new processing development brings together the ease of injection molding and the properties of magnetic materials. Precision rotors, rings, and even complex gears can now be molded from plastic-matrix compounds. Their magnetic strength is comparable to that of conventional ceramic magnets.

JOHN THEBERGE
Manager/R&D

BARRY ARKLES
Manager/Technical Development

DONALD KNABB
Product Development Engineer
LNP Corp.
Malvern, Pa.

UNTIL now, "magnetic" plastics have been available principally in sheet and in simple, extruded profiles—and these, only in flexible form. A new

technology, involving injection-moldable magnetic compounds and unique processing methods that provide precise, selective magnetization, offers far more design freedom and sophistication. The composites can be molded into complex shapes and, being rigid, can also serve as structural members.

Applications for the plastic-matrix magnetic composites go beyond simple mechanical functions such as clamps, latches (refrigerator doors, for

example), and bearing sleeves. These molded magnets are being used in energy-conversion applications including timing-motor rotors, magnetic indicators and sensors, and beam-focusing devices for television receivers and ion pumps.

In contrast to traditional cast metal magnets such as Alnico, plastic-matrix magnets are nonconductive and weigh less than one-third of the metal counterpart. Compared to ceramic magnets (fabricated by sintering and grinding), the plastic-matrix composites are much easier to fabricate—especially in thin sections—and are less brittle.

Configuration requirements present no problems: The shape versatility and dimensional control of injection molding easily provide magnetic rotors with integrally molded gear teeth and other magnets with bosses, holes, and other features needed for mounting or for mechanical functions.

Key to the magnetic properties of the molded parts lies in the techniques that orient the

Magnetic drive rotor for a water meter, above left, has 4-pole axial magnetization (as shown through magnetic viewer). A similar part, right, is a rotor for a subfractional-horsepower motor. This rotor has been processed to have a 30-pole radial magnetization configuration. Both parts are molded from a barium-ferrite-filled nylon compound and magnetized by in-mold orientation.

high loading of filler materials in the plastic matrix. This magnetization step is done in either of two ways—during molding or after molding—depending on final magnetic properties required. Molded composite magnets based on ferrite fillers can be produced by these techniques to yield energy products to one million gauss-oersteds; rare-earth composites with energy products to 3.5 times that value are available. This latter value exceeds that of calendered and extruded materials, middle-grade ceramics, and many Alnicos.

The Materials

Final physical, mechanical, and magnetic properties of a composite are determined by the base resin, type and amount of magnetic filler, and molding and magnetization techniques.

Resins: Base polymers used for molded magnets must have a high melt flow (be very fluid at melt temperature) to ensure that these highly loaded compounds fill and pack out the mold. Two materials that fit this requirement and that are used in commercially available magnetic compounds are nylon 6/10 and polyphenylene sulfide (PPS). Both also have sufficient mechanical strength in molded form to serve as structural members in addition to their magnetic function. Most present applications use the nylon-based compounds, but PPS is recommended for those that require higher temperature resistance, solvent resistance, or flame-retardancy characteristics.

Although not yet available

Two Ways to Magnetize Plastic-Matrix Compounds . . .

1. By Saturation (after molding)

a Unoriented Molded Part

b Magnetized Molded Part

Each individual magnetic particle has its preferred magnetic axis (indicated by arrows). For the molded part to achieve maximum strength, these axes must all be aligned in the same direction in which the final magnet requires its strength. The condition shown at **a** is typical of a magnetic part formed by normal molding techniques. Distribution of the magnetic axes of the particles is random.

A change occurs when a magnetic field is applied to the molded part, but those particles whose axes do not lie generally in the direction of the applied field are not strongly affected. The final magnet, **b**, has some strength in the desired direction, but its strength will be far from the potential maximum.

2. By Orientation (in the mold)

During molding, the magnetic particles are free to rotate physically and to become aligned with the applied magnetic field. As the polymer solidifies, the alignment is "locked-in." This technique — orientation — produces the strongest magnets. The table below shows the magnetic property differences between oriented and unoriented magnets (after saturation) molded from a barium-ferrite-loaded nylon 6/10 compound.

Property	Unoriented	Oriented
Remanence, B_r (gauss)	1,250	2,000
Coercivity, H_c (oersteds)	1,050	1,700
Intrinsic Coercivity, H_{ci} (oersteds)	2,500-3,000	2,800-3,500
Energy Product BH (10^3 gauss-oersteds)	350	850
Reversible Temperature		
Coef of Flux Density (%/°C)	-0.2	-0.2
Recoil Permeability	1.2	1.2

commercially, several materials that are normally classified as thermoplastic elastomers are also being evaluated for use as base resins for magnetic compounds. Two of these are polyester copolymers and polyurethanes. These polymers offer greater toughness and abrasion resistance than nylon or PPS.

Magnetic Fillers: The moldable magnetic compounds now available in commercial quantities are based on a barium-ferrite filler. As molding and magnetizing techniques are perfected, improved magnetic properties are being achieved with these compounds. Also, other ferrites are being developed that lend themselves more readily to this new method of fabricating magnets; these materials are expected to improve some magnetic properties by as much as 25%.

A recent breakthrough in magnet technology is the development of rare-earth magnets. Sintered rare-earth magnets (not polymer-bonded) are on the order of ten times better than ceramic magnets.

Experimental parts molded from plastic-matrix, rare-earth compounds exhibit magnetic properties equivalent to those of middle-grade ceramic magnets, Table 1. This represents about 60% of the potential strength of these materials.

Plastic-matrix compounds containing cobalt samarium (a rare earth) are available in developmental quantities for applications requiring higher magnetic properties than can be achieved with the ferrites. Since they are in the early stages of development, the rare-earth powders and compounds containing them are very expensive. As more applications are developed, however, increased volume will no doubt reduce the cost.

Table 1—Magnetic Properties Profile of a Typical Cobalt-Samarium Composite

Remanence, B_r (gauss)	2,000
Coercivity, H_c (oersteds)	4,800
Intrinsic Coercivity, H_{ci} (oersteds)	6,000-9,000
Energy Product, BH (10^3 gauss-oersteds)	3,500
Reversible Temperature	
Coef of Flux Density (%/°C)	-0.1

Fig. 1—Magnetization of an unoriented plastic-matrix molding can be achieved by placing the molding, end-to-end, between two bar magnets. This method produces very low strength magnets, however; in practice, high-strength, coil-generated fields are used to saturate (magnetize) the molded part.

Processing

Magnetic composites are injection-molded in conventional equipment. The same conditions that produce uniform, void-free moldings provide composites of highest magnetic quality. Normal injection temperatures and pressures used for the base resin involved also apply to the composites.

Low-Energy Magnets: Production of low-energy magnets—adequate for uses in instruments, meters, and small motors—involves simply exposing the molded, unoriented part to a magnetic field for less than a second. This field can be provided by metal bar magnets, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

In practice, however, full saturation usually cannot be achieved with simple bar magnets; in most cases, the magnetic field is provided by elec-

tromagnetic coils. For ferrite composites, typical saturation-energy levels are 8,000 to 12,000 oersteds. For cobalt-samarium composites this process is not practical at all because of the high magnetic field (25,000 to 60,000 oersteds) necessary for saturation.

Maximum-Energy Magnets: Saturation of unoriented molded parts cannot produce magnets having maximum magnetic properties. Parts that require such properties must have the magnetic filler particles oriented in the mold, before the plastic-matrix material has solidified.

While the in-mold orientation process requires a more complex mold (incorporating either permanent magnets or electromagnetic coils) a very low magnetic field (2,000 to 3,000 oersteds) is sufficient to mechanically orient ferrite-type filler particles in the liquid matrix. This is easily achieved

with high-strength Alnico magnets. Usually, higher than normal mold temperatures are used to provide sufficient time for the orientation to take place.

Molds utilizing permanent magnets for orientation have limitations, however. The continuous magnetic flux sometimes impedes or distorts material flow during mold filling. Also, since the magnet must contact the part, temperature fluctuations and wear can affect its strength which, in turn, alters the properties of the molded part. Finally, the orientation of rare-earth composites requires a higher-strength field (5,000 to 8,000 oersteds), which is beyond the range of most permanent magnets.

Most of these limitations are overcome by the use of single-pulse magnetic fields produced by electromagnetic coils. A typical pulse to orient ferrite particles is 7,000 to 8,000 oersteds for 0.01 to 0.05 sec; for cobalt samarium, a pulse of 12,000 to 15,000 oersteds is required.

Molding Equipment: Wear can be a serious problem in molding plastic-matrix magnetic compounds. The ferrites, particularly, are very hard and abrasive, and barrel and screw wear in a conventional screw-injection molding machine is four to six times that experienced with glass-fiber-reinforced molding compounds. Hard, wear-resistant alloys for these components are a must.

Molds are exposed to the same abrasive action; here too, the proper alloys must be used to provide adequate tool life as well as the necessary magnetic properties. For producing parts by the saturation method (after molding), wear is the sole governing factor that determines mold materials. For high-volume production, tungsten-carbide molds are often used; for lower quantity production, a

soft stainless steel is usually adequate.

For producing the higher magnetic strength parts (by in-mold orientation), selection of mold material is more critical. The orientation fields generated by either permanent magnets or electromagnetic coils built into the mold must be

properly conducted through the part during the molding cycle. Such molds are built from a combination of metals: Low magnetic reluctance metals conduct the fields where desired; these are surrounded by high magnetic reluctance metals to enclose the fields so they do not wander or become

In-line beam bender for color TV uses selectively magnetized, molded gear rings to adjust electron-beam direction. These rings, magnetized by the post-mold saturation method, replace a flat metal ring and provide an easier, more precise adjustment means, through an external gear knob (inset).

Fig. 2—In-mold magnetization, by orientation, of a plastic-matrix molding requires a complex mold construction to direct the magnetic field where it is needed. The ring-shaped part shown is being magnetically oriented radially.

dissipated. A typical mold of this type is shown in Fig. 2.

Finally, the use of permanent magnets and electromagnetic coils for orienting polymer composite materials is partially circumscribed in patent literature. The use of coils or permanent magnets may be allowable in some applications but not in others. Therefore, each potential application using these techniques should be examined carefully with respect to possible patent infringement.

Properties

Final magnetic properties of a molded composite can be varied widely through fabrication and orientation techniques. Applications do not always require the potential maximum values of all properties from a given compound.

In general, values of remanence, coercive force, and energy product (remanence times coercive force) of ferrite compounds increase linearly with filler content until the content approaches maximum loading. These properties also depend on the magnetization process. For example, un-oriented moldings can be exposed to magnetic fields at less than saturation values. Final properties depend both on the field applied and the susceptibility of the filler particles. Applications for which magnetic stability is important may require a two-step magnetization—maximum saturation, followed by demagnetization to a specific remanence value.

Magnets molded from today's commercially available compounds (ferrite filled) have energy products equivalent to those of cobalt steel and the lower-strength ceramic magnets. Alnico magnets have three to six times the remanence of highly oriented ferrite

Six-pole magnetic rotors for an electronic indicator replace components that were several times larger and that required assembly of the small "ears" to the outer rim. Compound is a nylon 6/10 resin, filled with barium ferrite; magnetization is by post-mold saturation.

Table 2—Physical and Mechanical Properties of Typical Magnetic Compounds

Property	ASTM Method	— Compound* —	
		A	B
Specific Gravity	D792	3.2	3.4
Thermal Coef of Linear Expansion (in./in.-°F)	D696	2.0×10^{-5}	1.1×10^{-5}
Thermal Conductivity Btu-in./hr-ft ² -°F	C177	3.2	8.7
Heat Deflection Temp at 264 psi (°F)	D648	230	400
Tensile Strength (psi)	D638	7,000	8,000
Impact Strength, Izod (ft-lb/in.)	D256		
Notched		0.6	0.8
Unnotched		2.0	1.6
Flexural Strength (psi)	D790	12,000	13,700
Flexural Modulus (10 ⁵ psi)	D790	12.5	25.1
Volume Resistivity (ohm-cm)	D257	1.8×10^8	1.2×10^7

*Compound A is LNP's Magnacomp A—a barium-ferrite filled nylon 6/10; compound B is Magnacomp AO—a barium-ferrite-filled polyphenylene sulfide.

moldings but only about one-third the coercive force.

The highest strength molded magnets are those containing cobalt samarium. These are more than three times stronger than the best ferrite-based molded magnets. Remanence of the cobalt-samarium molded magnets is comparable to that of most Alnicos, and coercive force is greater.

Mechanical properties of molded magnetic compounds,

Table 2, vary somewhat from those of the unreinforced base resins. Parts molded from the compounds have a higher modulus, lower impact strength, and lower coefficient of thermal expansion. Tensile and electrical properties remain about the same.

The maximally loaded composites meet UL 94 V-O standards, and those with less magnetic filler can be formulated to the same standard. MD

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MOLDED PLASTIC MAGNETS

LIQUID NITROGEN PROCESSING CORPORATION
PENNSYLVANIA

412 King Street, Malvern 19355/215-644-5200

CALIFORNIA

1831 E. Carnegie, Santa Ana 92705/714-546-2000

EUROPE

LNP Plastics Nederland B.V./Ottergeerde 24/
Raamsdonksveer/The Netherlands/01621•4350

In Canada: Fiberglas Canada Limited/48 St. Clair Ave. West/Toronto M4V1M7/416-924-9571